
BASUG LAW JOURNAL

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10495584>

SHARIA COURTS JURISDICTION AND ESTABLISHMENT OF THE FAMILY COURT CREATED UNDER THE CHILD RIGHTS ACT 2003: AN APPRAISAL

*Adamu Garba**

Abstract

Nigeria is a signatory to the Convention on the Rights of the Child and has made series of efforts to domesticate the treaty pursuant to section 12 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 sequel to which the Child Rights Act 2003 was signed into law. The Act creates and defines rights accorded to the children in Nigeria and provides for an enforcement mechanism of the rights in the form of a special court referred to as the Family Court among other things. The Court is to be established in all states of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory - Abuja at two levels: at the level of the High Court and at the magisterial level. The court has exclusive jurisdiction on all matters pertaining to children in Nigeria. However, the establishment of the court by the Act and its exclusive jurisdiction on all matters pertaining to children has obviously brought it into conflict with other courts established by the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), one of which is the Sharia Court of appeal of states and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and Sharia Courts validly established by legislatures of several states. This article attempts to examine the establishment of the aforementioned courts in

the light of their jurisdictions by employing doctrinal research methodology taking into account the constitutional powers of the legislatures to create courts in Nigeria and analyzing the constitutional consequences of vesting the Family Court with exclusive jurisdiction on all matters pertaining to children. Accordingly, it has been found that the act of subtracting the jurisdictions of the Sharia court of appeal and Sharia courts and exclusively vesting the Family Court with same is unconstitutional. It has been recommended that in order to fully solve the problem, the differences between the Act and some principles of Islamic law be reconciled to the extent that the provisions of the law can be enforced even in the sharia courts and also for states that apply Islamic law to incorporate the idea of Family Court into the Sharia courts mainstream system.

Keywords: Sharia Court, Childs Rights Act, Jurisdiction, Family Court

1.0 GENERAL INTRODUCTION

This article examines the constitutional implication of the establishment and exclusive jurisdiction of the Family Court on matters pertaining to children as provided by the Child Rights Act 2003, and also to analyse jurisdiction of the Sharia Courts of appeal of the states, of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja and the Sharia courts established by various states in the Northern part of the country. Accordingly, the paper is broadly divided into three parts: part one is introductory and comprises of the background to the study, statement of the research problem, research question, aim and objectives and the methodology employed in writing the article. Part two is the main body, and part three is the conclusion which contains the findings, observations and recommendations.

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The importance of raising children with good values, mental and physical health would never be overemphasized; this is a responsibility to both parents and society at large. Children do not only take care of their parents in future or be seen as leaders of tomorrow, they are also a trust in the hands of their parents and the society. The beneficiaries of the trust are the family, society and the world at large. Hence, if properly utilized, the outcome becomes fruitful and beneficial to all. It is against this background that every society irrespective of race, geography or creed attaches value to children with proper upbringing and background.

It is to be noted that, due to children's vulnerability and susceptibility to abuse, children could be easily maltreated, exploited or mishandled. In either case, the resultant effect never favors them or the society. It is in the light of this background that the international community made a giant effort towards the promotion, protection and development of the rights of the children by almost all Nation states in 1989.

However, it is good to note that, previous several efforts to have a universal instrument for better protection and promotion of rights of children did not yield the desired result and recognition until the year 1979 which was declared and designated as the "International Year of the Child." This was almost a decade after that year that the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted by the U.N General Assembly in 1989, and be into

force in the year 1990. Within that period, 140 nations signed the treaty.¹ Since then, the Convention has been ratified by every single U.N. member state in the world except Somalia.² However, on the 2nd of October, 2015, Somalia made a historic leap to uphold the rights of children by becoming the 196th country to ratify the Convention on the Rights of the Child.³ The United States of America has signed the convention on the 16th of February, 1995 but failed to ratify same as of today the 13th of October, 2023.⁴

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child is an international treaty that brought international, regional and national attention to the fact that children as human beings have the same rights as everyone else, and their rights deserved to be respected.⁵ The convention has made a profound impact on the attitudes of many nations towards their children by ensuring that state parties are obliged to undertake all legal, administrative and other appropriate measures to assist parents and other responsible parties in fulfilling obligations to children under the convention.⁶

Nigeria ratified the Children Convention in April 1991 and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child in July, 2001.⁷ It is to be noted that in 1996, Nigeria submitted its first report on the implementation of the Child Rights Convention to the United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child.⁸ One of the major recommendations made by the committee was for Nigeria to finally ensure the domestication of the Child Rights Convention, as this was necessary for its full implementation under the Nigerian system.⁹ Hence, a special committee was subsequently set up to harmonize the children bill with Nigerian religious and customary beliefs.¹⁰

* LL. B, BL, LL.M. LECTURER II, Department of Islamic law, Faculty of Law, Bauchi State University, Gadau. dangarba90@gmail.com

¹ The United Nations Status of Treaties Depository, accessed on the 13th of October, 2023

² Dankadai, L.B. The Legal Protection of Children against Exploitation of Child Labour in Nigeria. BUJPL Vol. 2 No. 1 June, 2010 P. 105

³ Information obtained from <https://somalia.un.org> > 91957-fifth-anniversary-somalia.

⁴ The United Nations Status of Treaties Depository, accessed on the 13th of October, 2023

⁵ Brown, P. (1999) P. 10 cited by Dankadai, L.B Ibid

⁶ The State of the World Children (1997) (UNICEF) P. 15 in Dankadai, L.B Ibid

⁷ Status of ratification of the Convention on the Rights of the Child

⁸ Akinwunmi, O.S Legal Impediments on the Practical Implementation of the Child Rights Act 2003, International Journal of Legal Information vol. 37, Article 10, 2010, Pg. 2

⁹ Committee on the Rights of the Child concluding observation on the conventions on the Rights of the Child CRC/C/15/Add 61 30/10/96 cited in Akinwumi, O.S supra

¹⁰ Ibid

Against this background, a draft of Child Rights Bill was enacted into law in Nigeria and the principles enshrined were basically based on the Convention on Rights of the Child and African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child as well as for renewed system of Juvenile Justice Administration to be prepared in 1990, after about ten years, the bill was eventually passed into law by the National Assembly in July 2003.¹¹ This was necessary because the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, precisely section 12 provides that for an international treaty to have effect in Nigeria, same must be domesticated as a national law.

Section 12 provides that:

“No treaty between the Federation and any other country shall have the force of law to the extent to which any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly.”

Furthermore, sub section 3 provides that:

“A bill of that nature shall not be presented to the President for an assent, and shall not be enacted unless it is ratified by a majority of all the House of Assembly in the Federation.”

However, it has been observed that this constitutional procedure has not been given due consideration.¹² Notwithstanding this non-observance, the bill was signed into Law by the President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Chief Olusegun Obasanjo in September 2003 and promulgated as the Child Rights Act, 2003.¹³

Basically, the Child Rights Act creates rights to be enjoyed by children in Nigeria, it protects the rights, proscribes certain conducts perceived to be harmful to children and provides implementation mechanisms for the enforcement and protection of the rights as well as providing universally standard procedure for handling juvenile offenders, among which is the Family Court created under section 149 of the Act.

¹¹ Akinwunmi, O.S Legal Impediments on the Practical Implementation of the Child Rights Act 2003, International Journal of Legal Information vol. 37, Article 10, 2010, Pg. 3

¹² Badamasuiy, J. Obligations and Rights of the Parents under the Child Rights Act: A Sharia Perspective, (2009) Zakara Communication Limited, Zaria Pg. 3

¹³ Akinwumi, O.S supra Pg. 4

It is worthy to note that the provisions of the Act supersede all other legislations that have bearing on the rights of the child.¹⁴ The Act is divided into 24 parts, 11 schedules and contains 273 sections. It seeks to harmonize all conflicts between the international and national laws about children in Nigeria.¹⁵ Having enacted this Law at the national level, the states are expected to finally adopt the Act for domestication as state laws. This is because child rights protection are not expressly provided in the exclusive list or the concurrent legislative lists, hence, it is highly advised for it to be part of the residual legislative powers of the states, thereby giving states exclusive responsibilities and jurisdiction to make laws relevant to their specific situations.¹⁶

On this issue, there are divergent opinions between legal scholars and practitioners. Some are of the view that the issue of children welfare and rights falls squarely within the residual list. It has accordingly been argued that since matters affecting children, or their welfare and rights are neither provided for in both the exclusive and concurrent legislative list as in part I and II of the Second schedule of the constitution, same must inferably be in the Residual list.¹⁷ Along this line, Akinwumi was of the view that the provisions of the Act supersede all legislations that have a bearing on the rights of the Child, having been enacted at the national level, the states are expected to formally adopt and adapt the Act for domestication as state laws. This is because issues of child rights protection are on the residual list of the Nigerian Constitution.¹⁸

To further amplify his point, the learned writer opined that Nigeria operates a federal system of government in which each of the thirty-six states of the federation is autonomous and equal to the others. Each state has its legislative system as stated by the constitution. Until the Child's Right Act is enacted into law in each of these legislative systems, it is not binding on the states. Hence, no court can prosecute violations of the Child Right Act in the states that have not enacted it. This view is not peculiar to this writer alone as many others shares same opinion, some have gone further to argue that matters of the

¹⁴ Ibid Pg. 6

¹⁵ Badamasuiy, J. Supra

¹⁶ Akinwumi, O.S supra

¹⁷ Olayiwola, O.S. Domestication of federal legislations: the non-justification of the call for domestication of the Child Rights Act: a misguided interpretation of constitutional provisions available at <http://ssn.com/abstract=3932145> Pg.3

¹⁸ Ibid

child are not contained in the exclusive and concurrent list, and thus leaving them in the residual list meant exclusively for the state, and the National Assembly by legislating on the subject matter, acted ultra vires, except where it (the National Assembly) is acting pursuant to the powers conferred on it by S.299 (a) of the Constitution, to act as the legislative house of the Federal capital territory.¹⁹

On this note, this research is of the opinion that it is erroneous to hold that the National Assembly acted ultra vires taking into consideration the provisions of section 12(2) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) which provides that the National Assembly may make laws for the Federation or any part thereof with respect to matters not included in the Exclusive Legislative List for the purpose of implementing a treaty. Therefore, banking on this provision, it can safely be argued that the National Assembly did not acted ultra vires by enacting the law, in spite of the fact that the issue is not in the Exclusive Legislative List.

Other legal scholars and practitioners on the other hand argues to the effect that the Child's Rights Act is a fundamental human rights legislation and the subject matter it covers (being the Rights of Children as well as their welfare) falls exclusively within the powers of the federal legislature i.e. The National Assembly as provided in Part 1 of the Second Schedule of the Constitution, and as such making it the only body empowered to legislate on the subject matter, and by reason of which the Act should apply throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria pursuant to Section 4 (2) of the same Constitution.²⁰

It however, appears to be that the issue falls into the residual legislative area and as such a need for states to implement the child rights law accordingly, as of today, all the states in the federation have passed various Child Rights Bills into law, including the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, with the exception of Gombe state.²¹

As highlighted above, in relation to the children in conflict with law, the Act lays down procedure for dealing with child offenders from the point of investigation and adjudication. It establishes a special court known as Family Court at the High Court and Magistrate Court

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Olayiwola, O.S. Domestication of Federal Legislations: The Non-Justification of the Call for Domestication of the Child Rights Act: A Misguided Interpretation of Constitutional Provisions available at <http://ssn.com/abstract=3932145> Pg.3

²¹ Ibid

levels; and confers on them jurisdiction to the exclusion of any other court in any matter civil or criminal relating to the children as specified in the Act.²² It empowers the Magistrate Court level of the court to impose maximum fine or imprisonment for offences created under the Act.²³

The High Court level has jurisdiction over offences carrying death penalty and those with terms of imprisonment of ten years and above.²⁴ A child is now to enjoy free legal services in all cases.²⁵ Specialized children police unit is also established and the Act mandates any person having dealing with children to undergo professional education, in service training, refresher courses, etc.

It also provides that in the determination of a case, the court shall be guided by the principle of conciliation, and shall encourage and facilitate the settlement of the matter in an amicable manner between the parties involved or likely to be affected by the results of the proceedings, such as the child or parents/guardians of the child or any other person having parental or other responsibility for the child.²⁶

The Court is also obliged to ensure the attendance in court of parents or guardians of the child or any other person with interest, for legal representation, to respect the legal status of the child, observe the right of the child to fair hearing, ensure the well-being of the child and avoid harassment to the child.²⁷ Appeals from the magistrate level lies to High Court level.²⁸ Further appeals shall lie to the Court of Appeal on any matter decided by the High Court in the same manner as appeals lie in respect of matters decided by the High Court.²⁹ This aspect of the Child Rights Act is adjudged to be a good development towards the protection of the rights of the child in Nigeria bearing in mind problems associated with administration of justice in Nigeria, particularly the issue of delay which the court, as

²²Abubakar; M. U Child Rights from the Perspectives of Islamic Law. www.gamjionline.com retrieved on the 11th Nov., 2014 P.

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Ahmed, A.B. The Law and Child Rights in Nigeria, Lagos, Malthouse Law Books (2015) P. 96

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Section 161 (1) of the Child Rights Act 2003

²⁹ Section 152 (5) of the Child Rights Act 2003

specialized court if established would significantly curtail. It has been established that the provisions in the Child Rights Act establishing the Family court is laudable.³⁰

It has been observed that the Child Rights Act that establishes the court and the new procedure apparently aims at providing universally acceptable standard child justice system in Nigeria as against the child justice system in force in the country which has been characterized with short comings such as: delay, abuse of the rights, lacks of adequate legal representation, insufficient resources and as well as obsolete and defective rules of procedure and evidence.³¹

The creation of Family Court under the Nigerian legal system is a new addition to the growing numbers of special courts under the Nigerian Courts system.³² Accordingly, some states, mostly of the southern part of the country have established the Family Court and most states in the northern part have not established same. Presently, more than 10 states have created Family Courts. Some states have also introduced the legal framework to use in the court³³ while many among them have indicated commitments to that effect, many have not.

For example, Kaduna state have adequately demonstrated its commitment in that regard through the Chairman, Kaduna State Justice for Children Coordination committee, Justice Darius Kobo who announced the establishment of the Family Court in the state. The Chairman made the announcement during a media engagement in Kaduna, saying it was created with a view to highlighting some of the achievements of the committee. He said the committee was set up by the state government to carry out a project by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and implemented by the State Ministry of Human Services and Social Development, in order to ensure justice for vulnerable children and individuals below the age of 18 who have come in conflict with the law. "The essence of this article is to

³⁰Bamgbose, O. Re-evaluating the Juvenile Child Justice System in Nigeria. a paper delivered at the 2014 Professor Jadesola Akande memorial lectures on 27th November.

³¹Ogunniran, I. A Centurial Legal History of Child Justice Reforms in Nigeria 1914-2014. *A Journal of Law, Crime and History* (2015) V. 2 P. 18

³²Beredugo, A. *J Nigerian Legal System: An Introductory note*; Malthouse Law Books, Lagos, 2009 ,3rd ed. P 176

³³ Ogunniran, I. Elusive Justice? An Assessment of a Child Justice in the Tripartite Court System in Nigeria *Acta Universitatis Danubius Juridica*, Vol. 10 No.3 2014 pg. 17

enable children know their rights and ensure their rights are duly protected to enable them access justice speedily where possible,” Justice Kobo explained.

He further stated that, after careful deliberations, the committee members realized that there was a dire need to have a Family Court to handle cases of children of 18 years and below in Kaduna State, which will be in line with the provisions of Kaduna State Child Welfare and protection law, domesticated since 2018.

The Chief Judge of Kaduna State, Justice Mohammed Lawal Bello had, before his retirement on April 24, signed the Family Court rules for the family court he designated in Kaduna, the courts are to be situated at Kaduna, Zaria and Kafanchan respectively.³⁴ In the same vein, the government of Sokoto state have, sequel to the passing into law the Child Rights Law, indicated its utmost interest in not only establishing the court, but making it to work effectively by providing adequate rules for the court. The Sultan of Sokoto and President General, Nigeria Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs (NSCIA), Muhammed Sa’ad Abubakar III, have declared his support for the Child Rights Law and the actualization of Family Court in the state.³⁵

Similarly, the federal government have also established Family Courts in 16 states to ensure child-friendly justice for children, either as victims or as offenders.³⁶ However, what is not clear on this development is whether the federal government is competent to establish such courts in the states. Accordingly, this may serve as a foundation for further research.

1.2 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

The Child Rights Act 2003 as an Act of the legislatures, by virtue of its section 149 and 150 has created an additional special court in Nigeria referred to as the Family court with the status of a High court, to be established at the states and the Federal Capital territory, Abuja. The same Child rights Act by virtue of section 151 and 162 accorded the Family court with an exclusive jurisdiction on all matters pertaining children. This part has by

³⁴ A Printed Report of the Radio Nigeria, May,20,2022 available at info@radionigeria.gov.ng accessed on the 13th of October 2023 around 2:00 pm

³⁵The IDEAL: Sultan Backs Child Rights Law and Family Court in Sokoto State, October 4th, 2023 available at [@theideal.ng](https://www.theideal.ng) accessed on 13th of October, 2023 around 2:15 pm

³⁶ The Punch Newspaper: FG Establishes Family Court in 16 States, 25th May, 2023, available at [punching.com](https://www.punching.com).2023 accessed on the 13th of October,

implication robbed the Sharia court of Appeal of the states, the Federal Capital Territory Abuja and of Sharia courts established by state laws jurisdiction on issues that relates to children subject to Islamic law of personal status.

Section 149 & 150 of the Act read thus:

Section 149:

There shall be established at each state of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja a court known as the Family Court (in this Act referred to as the court) for the purposes of hearing and determining matters relating to the children.

Section 150:

The court shall be at two levels:

- 1- The Court as a division of the High Court at the High Court Level*
- 2- The Court as a Magistrate Court at the Magistrate Level.*

Section 151 of the Act provides:

Subject to the provision of this Act and in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred on it by any other law, the court shall have unlimited jurisdiction to hear and determine:

- (a) Any civil proceeding in which the existence of or extent of a legal right, power, duty and liability, privilege, interests, obligation or claim in respect of a child is in issue; and*
- (b) Any criminal proceeding involving or relating to any penalty, forfeiture, punishment or other liability in respect of an offence committed by a child or against the interest of a child.*

The Act further expressly confers exclusive jurisdiction on the court in respect of all matters pertaining to children under section 162 which provides:

- (1) No other court except the Family Court, shall exercise jurisdiction in any matter relating to children as specified in this Act.*

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTION

From the foregone, the following research question is formulated:

Is it valid for an Act of the National Assembly to vest other court with exclusive jurisdiction on matters which the constitution already conferred such to the Sharia Courts of Appeal and Sharia courts validly established by States?

1.4 RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of writing this article is to investigate the constitutional validity of vesting the Family court with a jurisdiction already given to the Sharia Courts of appeal and other Sharia courts.

Accordingly, this task is set to be achieved through the following objectives:

- (i) Discussing the constitutional powers of the legislatures to create courts in Nigeria.
- (ii) Analyzing the constitutional consequences of vesting the Family Court with exclusive jurisdiction on all matters pertaining to children in the light of the jurisdictions of the Sharia courts of appeal and Sharia Courts.

1.5 METHODOLOGY

The article is conducted using information and theories extracted from both relevant primary and secondary sources of mainly legal documents. From the primary sources, the authorities include the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, the Child Rights Act, 2003 and judicial pronouncements from Nigerian superior courts of record. Materials from the secondary sources includes text books written by legal scholars, articles in journals, ordinary articles and any useful publications.

2.0 THE MAIN BODY

2.1 THE POWERS OF THE NIGERIAN LEGISLATURES TO CREATE COURTS

Nigeria was given independence in 1960. Prior to that period, the colonial masters ruled by ordinances and proclamations issued by them. But with the attainment of independence, Nigeria operated a parliamentary system of government from 1960-1966 which is referred to as the Nigerian first republic, operating under the 1960 Independence Constitution and subsequently the 1963 Republican Constitution before the military struck and ended the era. At that period, Nigerian legislatures made laws for the good governance and public welfare. The members of the parliament were elected into the parliament under the platform of various political parties. At that period, one of the giant efforts of the central

parliament was amending the constitution from the constitutional monarchy to the Republican Constitution of 1963. One of the achievements of that change was the final severance of the Nigeria's judicial system from that of the England by making the Supreme Court of Nigeria to become the final appellate court in the country as against going to the West African Court of Appeal (W.A.C.A) and finally the England Privy Council.³⁷

When the military took over the reins of power in January 1966, they became the leaders of the country; wielding both the Executive and Legislative powers. This arrangement had the Supreme Military Council the highest law-making body, and their laws which are referred to as "Decrees" covered the whole country. With the creation of states, Military Governors were appointed to govern the states. They also made laws for the respective states they governed in form of "Edicts".³⁸ In relation to creation of courts, the military used to create courts where there was a need for that, and sequel to which various courts were created such as the Federal Revenue Court in 1973 which eventually became the Federal High Court,³⁹ Federal Court of Appeal in 1976 and the National Industrial Court in 1976.⁴⁰

The Military also used to establish tribunals to perform judicial or quasi-judicial functions such as the Robbery and Fire Arms Tribunals,⁴¹ Special Tribunal for the Trial of Kidnappers, Lynching Cases,⁴² Currency Offences Tribunals established under the Counterfeit Currency (Special Provision) Decree 1974 and Rent Tribunals. Other bodies established to exercise judicial or quasi-judicial function includes Joint Tax Board, established by section 27 (1) of the Income Tax Management Act; the Body of Appeal Commissions established under section 55 of the Companies Income Tax Act 1961; The Legal Practitioners Disciplinary Committee established under section 9 of the Legal Practitioners Decree of 1975 etc.

After the return of civil rule in 1979 and with the coming into force of the 1979 Constitution, courts were established and enumerated in the Constitution ranging from the Supreme Court to the Court of appeal, Federal High Court, State High Courts, the Sharia Courts and

³⁷Malemi, E, The Nigerian Constitution law, Lagos, Princeton Publishing co. Ltd pg.27

³⁸The Federal Revenue Court was established by the Federal Revenue Court Decree No. 13 of 1973

³⁹ Established pursuant to the Provisions of the 1979 Constitution

⁴⁰ Decree No.7 of 1976

⁴¹ Established on the 1st October 1976 by the Constitution Amendment Decree No. 2 of 1976

⁴² Established under the Robbery and Fire Arms Special Provision Decree of 1970

Customary Courts of Appeal for states that needed them. The legislatures were then empowered by the constitution to create and abolish courts apart from the ones already established by the constitution.

That remained the arrangement until the military bounced back in 1983 which disrupted the system and dismantled the democratic constitutional authorities including the legislatures and reverted back to the pre-1979 arrangement. Several tribunals were established at that time to try corrupt politicians and for other reasons which remained the practice from 1983 to 1999 when the military held sway as the leaders of the country.

With the return to democracy in 1999 a new constitution came into force on the 29th May, 1999. The 1999 Constitution was just a re-incarnation of the 1979 Constitution with some amendments. Section 6 of the 1999 Constitution categorically vested the judicial power of the Federation in the courts and Chapter VII (seven) of the Constitution is dedicated to the judicature. The constitution enumerated the superior courts of records in Nigeria and provides for their jurisdictions, composition and appeal structures. It enumerated courts to be the Supreme Court, the Court of Appeal, Federal High Court, State High Courts, Customary and Sharia Courts of appeal and later the National Industrial Court.

2.2 THE POWERS UNDER THE CONSTITUTION OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA 1999.

The legislatures in Nigeria under the various laws that establish them are empowered to create and abolish courts. However, the provisions of the 1999 Constitution would be used to discuss the powers therein. The legislature here includes both the National Assembly which comprises of the Senate and the House of Representatives and the State Houses of Assembly. The power in the constitution could be categorized into the Express and Implied Powers.

2.2.1 EXPRESS POWER

This is the power given to the legislatures expressly by section 6 of the constitution, particularly section 6(4) thereof which after enumerating the courts established by the constitution, goes further and expressly empowers the legislatures to establish other courts where there is need with however a subordinate jurisdiction to that of a High Court.

The section provides as follows:

Nothing in the foregoing provisions of this section shall be construed as precluding:

- a) *The National Assembly or any House of Assembly from establishing courts other than those to which this section relates with the subordinate jurisdiction to that of High Court:*
- b) *The National Assembly or any House of Assembly which does not require it from abolishing any court which it has*
- c) *Power to establish or which it has brought into being.*

2.2.2 IMPLIED POWER

On the other hand, this is the power that could be inferred from the general powers of the legislature to make laws for the peace, order and good governance for the Federation. This power is given under section 4(1) and (2) of the constitution as follows:

(1) The Legislative powers of the Federal Republic of Nigeria shall be vested in the National Assembly for the Federation which shall consist of a Senate and the House of Representative.

(2) The National Assembly shall have power to make laws for the peace, order and good government of the Federation or any part thereof with respect to any matter included in the Exclusive Legislative List set out in Part I of the Second Schedule to this Constitution.⁴³

In the exercise of the above enumerated powers, several courts have been established by both the Federal and state legislatures. In this respect, the federal legislatures created the Family court by an Act of the National Assembly in 2003. Similarly, pursuant to the above cited provisions, various states that apply Islamic law have established Sharia courts for the smooth running of the administration of Islamic law.

2.3 SHARIA COURTS, SHARIA COURTS OF APPEALS AND THEIR JURISDICTIONS

Sharia courts were duly established by state laws pursuant to section 6(4) of the constitution to exercise both criminal and civil jurisdictions. In civil proceedings, the court shall exercise jurisdiction in Islamic law in which the existence or extent of a legal right,

⁴³ The Exclusive Legislative list consists of 68 Items ranging from the Accounts of the Government of the Federation to any matter incidental or supplementary to any matter mentioned elsewhere in the list.

power, duty and liability, privilege, interest, obligation or claim is in issue.⁴⁴ On criminal matters however, Sharia courts are empowered to exercise jurisdiction relating to any offence, penalty, forfeiture, punishment or other liability in respect of an offence committed by any person or against state.⁴⁵

Section 275 of the Constitution provides that there shall be for any State that requires it a Sharia Court of Appeal which shall consist of a Grand Kadi and such other number of the Kadis as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state. Pertaining to its jurisdiction, section 277 of the constitution provides that the Sharia Court of Appeal of a state shall, in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred upon it by the law of the state, exercise such appellate and supervisory jurisdiction in civil proceedings involving questions of Islamic personal law which the court is competent to decide, these includes:

- i. Islamic personal law regarding a marriage concluded in accordance with that law, a question relating to the validity or dissolution of such a marriage or a question that depends on such a marriage and relating to family relationship or the guardianship of an infant;⁴⁶
- ii. Where all the parties to the proceedings are Muslims, any question of Islamic personal law regarding a marriage, including the validity or dissolution of that marriage, or regarding family relationship, a foundling or the guardianship of an infant;
- iii. Any question of Islamic personal law regarding a Waqf, gift, will or succession where the endower, donor, testator or deceased person is a Muslim;
- iv. Any question of Islamic personal law regarding an infant, a prodigal or person of unsound mind who is a Muslim or the maintenance or guardianship of a Muslim who is physically or mentally infirm; or Where all the parties to the proceedings, being Muslims, have requested the court that hears the case in the first instance to determine that case in accordance with Islamic personal law, or any other question.⁴⁷

⁴⁴ See for example section 5 of the Sharia Court (Administration of Justice and Certain Consequential Changes) Law, Cap.S4 laws of Jigawa State 2012

⁴⁵ Ibid

⁴⁶ Section 277(2) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)

⁴⁷ Ibid

In the same token, section 260 and 262 of the Constitution made same provisions for the Sharia Court of appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Therefore, in essence, Sharia Courts, the Sharia Courts of Appeal of States and the Federal Capital Territory Abuja are the competent courts recognized by the courts to exercise appellate jurisdiction over matters pertaining to children subject to Islamic family law.

However, Family court, on the other hand, has been vested with exclusive jurisdiction in matters such as guardianship of a child, adoption, ward ship, custody of a child, child Labour, Child betrothal, Child marriage, Fosterage, maintenance of child; maternity and paternity among other things.

This crucial aspect of the court appears to be problematic because by vesting Family Court with exclusive jurisdiction over the above matters, the constitutional jurisdictions of the Sharia Court Appeal of the States and of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja on questions of Islamic Personal Law and questions of Customary Law, particularly in respect to issues of marriage, guardianship of a child, adoption, fosterage, paternity among other things as they relate to children subject to Islamic Personal Law are subtracted or ousted to some extent in favour of the Family Court.

This act of subtracting or ousting the jurisdiction of courts already established by law; particularly established by the constitution itself in favour of another court without repealing or amending the earlier law that established the affected court was held to be unconstitutional. In the case of *Oloba V. Akereja*⁴⁸ the Supreme Court held that:

“No legislature can subtract from or reduce the jurisdiction of a court established under the constitution save by way of constitutional amendment. Any legislation purporting to have that effect shall be void to the extent of its inconsistency with the relevant section of the constitution conferring jurisdiction on the particular court concerned”.

However, it seems some states have taken steps to avoid this problem through their various Child Rights Law. For example, The Jigawa State Child Rights law establishes a Family court for the purpose of entertaining matters relating to children. Similarly, in the

⁴⁸ (1988)3, NWLR (PT.84) 503

proposed Child Rights Bill of Borno state, Family courts are of two levels: High court/Sharia Court of Appeal and Magistrate court/Upper Sharia court. In these instances, it is implicit that the Sharia and Magistrate courts have concurrent jurisdiction, in other words, litigants can appear before either of the courts. Furthermore, appeal shall lie from Magistrate to High court and Sharia to Sharia Court of Appeal.

It is our opinion that in these states, creation of Family courts was meant to fulfill all righteousness, as it is most likely that Sharia courts will be the adjudicator on matters relating to the children.⁴⁹ In addition, the applicable laws and rules of procedure for hearing and determination of all civil and criminal proceedings before the courts are as prescribed under Islamic Law.⁵⁰

Under the Child Rights Act, the Family Courts at both the Magistrate and High Courts shall be duly constituted if it consists of a judge and two assessors and one of the assessors must be learned in child psychology education. Also, the Chief Justice of Nigeria may make rules regulating procedure in the Courts.⁵¹ It is clear that judges with different educational backgrounds applying different rules of procedure operate in both courts. Whilst one is trained in Islamic Law, the other is trained in Common Law and Nigerian Laws. It is therefore not surprising that decisions even on the same issues affecting children will be poles apart under the two systems. The implication as in the Jigawa and Borno examples given above, notwithstanding the Child Rights Laws, decisions affecting children will be based on Islamic Law *simpliciter* for children who appear in Sharia courts.⁵²

Moreover, the Child Protection Law of Jigawa State⁵³ did not elaborate on the circumstances where a matter pertaining to a child may go to Sharia Court of the Family Court or the Magistrate Court of the latter. With reference to Sokoto State however, the then State Governor, Aminu Waziri Tambuwal has signed the Child Protection Bill into Law passed by the State Assembly on 11th November, 2021 to enhance the condition of every child across the state.⁵⁴ The state has since been working to reconcile the content of the law with

⁴⁹ Ogunniran, I. Child Rights Act Versus Sharia Law in Nigeria: Issues, Challenges and Way Forward Pg.5

⁵⁰ Ibid

⁵¹ Ibid

⁵² Ibid

⁵³ Child Protection Law of Jigawa State, 2021

⁵⁴ Voice of Nigeria, 23rd November 2021 available at <http://von.gov.ng> accessed on the 13th of October, 2023

the prevalent religion and culture of the state for effective enforcement of the law, including the Family Court.

3.0 CONCLUSION

In a bid to comply with an international obligation, and promote the welfare of children, Nigeria has signed into law, the Child Rights Act in 2003, and accordingly created a special court called the Family Court as an implementation mechanism of the provisions of the Act. The Court is created at the High court and Magisterial levels and has been vested with both criminal and civil jurisdictions on matters pertaining to children in Nigeria. States of the Federation are expected to create the courts by state laws because matters concerning children rights and welfare are state issues. The Act has vested the Family court with exclusive civil jurisdiction on matters pertaining to children. However, issues of children, subject to Islamic faith, that involves their rights, welfare and protection are constitutionally recognized as part of Islamic law of personal status and accordingly subject to the appellate jurisdiction of the Sharia Court of appeal of the states and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and by extension the original jurisdiction of Sharia courts validly established by various state laws.

3.1 FINDINGS

- i. It is not valid for an Act of the National assembly to subtract the jurisdictions of the Sharia Courts of appeal of the states, the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and the Sharia Courts of the various states and exclusively vest same in the Family Court without constitutional amendment; and the act is found to be unconstitutional; reliance is hereby placed on the judicial authority of *Oloba v. Akereja* cited above.
- ii. In an attempt to solve the problem pointed above, and considering the religious and cultural peculiarities of most of the states of northern part of the country, Jigawa and Borno States have integrated the Family Court into both the High Court and the Sharia Courts structures, such action produces a plural child justice system that appears to be somehow not in accordance with the intent of the Child Rights Act and Convention on the Rights of the Child.

3.2 OBSERVATIONS

- i. It is hereby observed that among other things, unless this issue of conflict of jurisdiction between Family Court and Sharia Courts is resolved, it would be difficult to establish the Family court, particularly in the states that establishes Sharia courts and applies Islamic law.
- ii. It is further observed that the problem highlighted above is linked to the differences between some of the provisions of the Child Rights Act and the principles of Islamic law which made the provisions of the Act inapplicable in Sharia Courts.

3.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. It is hereby recommended that in order to fully utilize the idea of having a special court like Family court, especially in the states that applies Islamic law, a Sharia Court should be created and fashioned as a Sharia Family court with jurisdiction on matters pertaining to children subject to Islamic law marriage. This is to ensure speedy dispensation of adjudications on children issues. Appeals from the Sharia Family Court shall then be made to lie to the Sharia Court of appeal of the states and then upward up to the Court of appeal and the Supreme Court respectively.
- ii. It is further recommended that the contents of the Child Rights Act should be in consonance with the principles of Islamic law, such that the provisions of the Child Rights Law can be applicable even in the Sharia Courts.